

EFFECT OF PEER PRESSURE ON ANTISOCIAL BEHAVIORS AMONG STUDENT OF ZANZIBAR SCHOOL OF HEALTH

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7263332>

Published Date: 29-October-2022

Abstract: This study focused on assessing the influence of peer pressure on student social behavior. The consideration of this area of the study was coherently driven up by some facts existing of negative influence of peer pressure among college students. Specifically, the objectives of study were to investigate the causes of peer pressure on antisocial behaviors among students of Zanzibar school of health, to examine the effect of peer pressure on antisocial behaviors among student of Zanzibar school of health and to determine which sex is mostly affected by the consequences of peer pressure at Zanzibar school of health. Social interaction theory was considered more appropriate in this study. The researchers conducted the survey among the students in Zanzibar school of Health which includes 171 respondents who completed the survey. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used in this study. The study used questionnaires for students in quantitative method by compiling, editing, coding, classified and tabulating the data using descriptive statistic then drawing conclusion Then the raw data from questionnaires was entered in the SPSS version 20 program so as to be analyzed. Focused group interview in qualitative method for lectures was applied as the main data collection instrument. This study found out that peer pressure has greater influence on student's social behaviors and it has a greater effect in their academic life. The study also reveal that gender of the pupils, had significant impact on the peer influence. The following recommendations if put in place will contribute to the improvement of the ministry of education should emphasis on the important of school guidance and counseling so as to help students reduce the effects of peer pressure and negative behaviors. Institute management should keep counselors to each among the five courses so as to help the students to overcome their social and educational challenges, Students and school should be made aware of the effects of peer pressure as it greatly influences in their academic status.

Keywords: Peer pressure, peer group, antisocial behaviors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Treynor (2009) pressure is the influence exerted by a peer group or an individual encouraging other individuals to change their attitudes, values or behaviors in order to conform to group norms. Social groups affected include membership groups in which individuals are formally members. Among adults, it is considered a rare phenomenon, though with the increasing competition for resources and personal progress, adult peer pressure is an emerging area of interest. Peer pressure is not always a bad thing because peer groups can actually have a very positive influence on individual's behavior. For some adults, a peer group can be a source of security, a learning opportunity and a source of encouragement among others. The difference between negative and positive peer pressure is the impact it has on the person. While most forms of influence don't necessarily feel comfortable for the person on the receiving end, the outcomes of the influence are likely to be mostly positive. Positive peer pressure results in a person feeling better, healthier or happier. Negative peer pressure on the other hand, results in people feeling unhappy, unwell or uncomfortable. People give in to peer pressure because they want to be

International Journal of Novel Research in Interdisciplinary StudiesVol. 9, Issue 5, pp: (19-25), Month: September – October 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

accepted and fit in a group. Conformity may create problems when peers influence each other to participate in deviant activities.

Peer pressure influence is both national and international problem which affect youth all around the world. Efforts to define more clearly the nature of the peer group influence have produced interesting trends, if not clearly established relationships. Several developmental studies on adolescents indicate that, relative to children and adults, they are sensitive and at a high response to a variety of social stimuli such as facial expressions and social feedback (Burnett et al., 2011).

Caldwell & Darling (2019) recognized as a major contributor to the initiation of drug use, particularly in adolescence. This has been shown for a variety of substances, including nicotine and alcohol. While this link is well established, moderating factors do exist. For example, parental monitoring is negatively associated with substance use; yet when there is little monitoring, adolescents are more likely to succumb to peer coercion during initiation to substance use, but not during the transition from experimental to regular use. extended this work by finding that peer pressure was a factor leading to risk in the context of social gatherings with little parental monitoring, and if the individual reported themselves as vulnerable to peer pressure.

According to Molders et al. (2019), adolescents utilize their time to conduct homework to communicate with their peer group members through social media using smartphones and laptops. They usually go forth from their reading to replying to texts and watching TV programs that take full attention from school work. Peer pressure causes multitasking, forcing teenagers to reduce their attention to school work, reducing their school productivity.

Another study conducted by Kessler (2012) In Tanzania, showed that university students engage in bad groups like cannabis smoking, alcoholism, theft, sexual promiscuity but also encourage young people who do not have bad habits to join bad groups that lead to low academic performance. Great effort made by the government to ensure influence of peer group in adolescent students has a greater magnitude on behavior and decision making. For instance, Swiss Centre for International Health in collaboration with Ministry of Education and Vocation Training in Tanzania (MoEVT) provided a nine-year program that aimed at counseling peer adolescents in Tanzania from (2003- 2012) in Mtwara, Lindi, Mbeya, Morogoro, Ruvuma, Iringa, and Kilimanjaro regions. Parents, teachers, media and community in general also play huge role in fighting against peer groups and anti-social behaviors. Many studies have been conducted on the influence of peer pressure globally but only few studies published in Zanzibar. Therefore, this study specifically was conducted in Zanzibar where there is an increase of the number of cases mainly facing adolescent students, whereby many of these cases were caused by peer pressure influence, as recorded in the ministry of education and vocational training educational policy of Zanzibar (2006). Peer pressure has been categorized on positive and negative influence, most of the studies indicate that many adolescents schools students influenced by negative peer pressure that lead to antisocial behaviors, this study, therefore, was assessing the influence of peer pressure on student anti-social behaviors in higher learning institution in Zanzibar school of health.

Specific objectives

To examine the effect of peer pressure on antisocial behaviors among student of Zanzibar school of health.

Hypothesis: Peer pressure and antisocial behaviors influence students in Zanzibar School of Health.

Statement of the Problem

The influence of peer pressure and antisocial behaviors has been reported to be a major problem in Zanzibar. Ministry of education and vocational training educational policy of Zanzibar 2006 indicate that boys drop out of school and early marriage to girls caused by lack of motivation to learn and peer pressure influence where evidence in 2009-2016 indicate that 23% of girls had sex before the age of 18. ZBC radio news report on “mawiyo” daily reporting several cases of consequences of antisocial behaviors such as sexual abuse cases, drug abuse cases, theft behaviors and also depression and trauma which some of them cause death to the youth whereby most of these cases include students between 15-22 years however some cases of bellow 15 years and above 22 years have also been reported. And these cases have negative effects to youths and their families, which is the main reason that the researcher is proposing to conduct this research on assesses how far peer pressure influences student’s anti-social behavior in Zanzibar.

Despite initiatives and efforts taken by the Zanzibar government and non-government organization through different campaigns on the importance of self-awareness campaigns on the negative effects of using illicit drugs; campaign on the sexual transmitted infections but the problem still increasing. Although many studies have been conducted on peer pressure influence on secondary students in Tanzania few studies have been conducted in Zanzibar .Therefore this study aiming at

filling this gap of information by assessing the influence of peer pressure on students’ social behaviors in Zanzibar school of health.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Introduction

The chapter presents the literature review related to this study. The researcher presents the critical review of a diverse range of literature relevant to the research topic. The review sought that both peer pressure and antisocial behaviors influence students at Zanzibar School of Health. The theoretical framework was presented and captured the theory that informed the study. The conceptual framework showed the relationship between independent and the dependent variable. The chapter also presented the empirical review, critique of existing literature relevant to this study and the final section was the summary of the chapter and the research gaps.

Theoretical Framework

A theoretical framework is a collection of interrelated ideas based on theories. It is a reasoned set of propositions, which are derived from and supported by data or evidence (Kombo and Tromp, 2006). This study was guided by theory of psychosocial theory, social interaction theory and cognitive Patterson, Reid & Dishion (1992) social learning theory which explains that peer selection and peer influence effects are both important in the formation and continuation of normal peer relationships as well as deviant peer groups.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study describes the relation between variables where peer pressure as independent variables focusing on influencing student in either negative or positive peer pressure.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Empirical review

According to Kevin (2012), students and pupils alike tend to hang out with others with similar aspirations (Kevin, 2012). Through gender-role socialization, group members learn about sex differences, social and cultural expectations. The previous studies have cited girls to be influenced by peer influence than boys and this could be the case with peer influence on the academic performance. Girls almost forms peer groups throughout 21 their lives but it is more pronounced at the adolescent stage. The preference for girls to be in peer groups is attributed to the fact that girls prefer to have high quality peer relationship that provide support in all areas of their lives including the academic work (Miller & Birch, 2007; Kinder Mann, 2007).

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According to Xu Lin(2005), peer influence in all facets of the adolescent occur at early ages of the adolescent stage and it is during this time that peer relations is very problematic for them. Literature has suggested that there is considerable individual variation regarding cognitive skill development during adolescents as it relates to peer influence which eventually as an impact on the academic performance. The adolescents who have positive peer influence generate more alternative solutions to problems including those related to school work. This is because peer group is the source of information needed to be empowered academically, vocationally, psychologically or otherwise and give the feedback about the appropriateness of their emotions especially when adolescents are highly stressed or under stressed (Ammermueller & Pischke, 2006).

The negative implication of the peer influence at adolescent is the engagement of the 23 students on negative behavior. At the age of fourteen years, students are twice likely to engage in risky, self-destructive behavior than eighteen year olds are and if not controlled, may lead to poor academic performance. If the students at that age are regulated either by schools and parental regulations, by eighteen years, they become more autonomous and one has clear aspirations of where he or she wants to go and how to get there (Foster, 2006).

In nutshell, whatever happens during this developmental stage goes a long way in affecting the individual's academic performance. Boucher, Bramoule, Djebbari & Fortonl (2010) found out that in most cases peer influence at adolescent stage affects negatively the students' achievement in school. As children grow, develop and move into early adolescence, involvement with peer and attraction of peer identification increases. Peer mobilizes their adolescent energies and motivate for success to get cultivated hence improving the academic performance (Enomoto, Ritter, Leiderman, Roberts & Fraleigh, 2000; Tope, 2011).

Research Gaps

Study conducted by Mosha, 2017, Waukundi, 2016 and Kiwale, 2017 indicate many studies have been conducted on peer pressure influence on secondary students in Tanzania. The study reveals that peer pressure play significant roles on shaping students in antisocial behaviors. Wan Munira Binti Wan Jaafar (2017) Furthermore, more studies should be conducted on other variables considering the fact that psychosocial factors.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study is a descriptive research study. This design seek descriptive information on the influence of peer pressure on student's antisocial behaviors. This type of descriptive research employed in this study is the survey research technique. The reason for the use of survey technique is because, questionnaires was administered on students. The survey is an attempt to collect data from members of a population in order to determine the current (influence of peer pressure) status of the population with respect to one or more variable(s). The study employed stratified sampling technique in selecting the respondents.

This study used questionnaires for students in quantitative method and focused group interview in qualitative method for lectures as the main data collection instrument .In developing the questionnaire items, the fixed choice and open ended formats were used.

The sample size of this study comprised 171respondents, equivalent to 57%. Data was calculated from the total population 300 people by using the Slovin's formula.

Table 3.1: Sample size of the profile.

Participants	Population	Percent %
Senior administrators	20	11.7%
Lecturers	21	12.3%
Students	130	76%
Total	171	100 %

More over the data was statistical techniques such as percentages, mean, frequency, standard deviation, tables and bar charts by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 20 so as to get numerical data presentation. Qualitative methods were focused on experiences and processes with an emphasis on context. It tends to be exploratory and was analyzed by identifying themes and concepts.

4. FINDINGS

This chapter analyses the data collection from administration of questionnaire with simple percentage method of data analysis and the findings are discussed below in the table.

The result have been presented due to the research questions. To achieve this objective the researcher, also distribute questionnaire and done interview to the respondent’s in order to know how this issue effects the respondents. The study come up with the results as most of respondents agree using of drugs and smokes mostly influence by peer pressure, this cause by poor parents-child relationship and according to the culture many parents are not willing talking with their children on this matter.

Table 1: peer pressure and antisocial behaviors increase negative behaviors and attitudes

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	4	2.3	2.3	2.3
	Agree	102	58.6	59.6	62.0
	Not sure	42	24.1	24.6	86.5
	Disagree	23	13.2	13.5	100.0
Total		171	100	100.0	

The findings from table 1 revealed that most of the respondents strongly agree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors increase negative behaviors and attitudes, while 8 (4.6%) strongly disagree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors increase negative behaviors and attitudes, and 5 (2.9%) are not sure whether peer pressure and antisocial behaviors increase negative behaviors and attitudes.

Table 2: Peer pressure leads to drinking or drug use

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly agree	68	39.3	39.8	39.8
	Agree	70	40.5	40.9	80.7
	Not sure	14	8.1	8.2	88.9
	Disagree	7	4.0	4.1	93.0
	Strongly disagree	12	6.9	7.0	100.0
	Total	171	98.8	100.0	
Missing	System	2	1.2		
Total		173	100.0		

The findings from table 2 showed that most of the respondents strongly agree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to drinking or drug use, while 12 (6.9 %) strongly disagree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to drinking or drug use and 14 (8.1 %) are not sure whether peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to drinking or drug use.

Table 3: peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense with parents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	58	33.7	33.9	33.9
	Agree	77	44.8	45.0	78.9
	Not sure	19	11.0	11.1	90.1
	Disagree	17	9.9	9.9	100.0
	Total	171	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.6		
Total		172	100.0		

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Vol. 9, Issue 5, pp: (19-25), Month: September – October 2022, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

The findings from table 3 revealed that most of the respondents (77, 48.8%) agree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents, while 7(4.0%) strongly disagree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents and 14 (8.1%) are not sure whether peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents.

Table 4: peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to anxiety

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	41	23.8	24.0	24.0
	Agree	61	35.5	35.7	59.6
	Not sure	35	20.3	20.5	80.1
	Disagree	21	12.2	12.3	92.4
		13	7.6	7.6	100.0
	Total	171	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.6		
Total		172	100.0		

The findings from table 4 revealed that most of the respondents agree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to anxiety, while 21 (12.5 %) strongly disagree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents, and 35 (20.1%) are not sure whether peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents.

Table 5: peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to depression

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	41	23.8	24.0	24.0
	Agree	65	37.8	38.0	62.0
	Not sure	36	20.9	21.1	83.0
	Disagree	10	5.8	5.8	88.9
		19	11.0	11.1	100.0
	Total	171	99.4	100.0	
Missing	System	1	.6		
Total		172	100.0		

The findings from table 6 revealed that most of the respondents (102, 58.6%) agree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to depression, while 23 (13 %) strongly disagree that peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents, and 32 (24.11%) are not sure whether peer pressure and antisocial behaviors lead to tense relationships with parents.

Recommendations for Further Research

The research recommended the following areas for further studies:

- Further study should be carried out on peer pressure as a predictor of risky sexual behaviors of secondary school adolescents.
- Students' antisocial behaviors and academic performance in Zanzibar

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